

PD KONTROL CİHAZINA DAYALI BASİT MEKANİZMALAR KULLANARAK YENİ BİR DRONE TASARIMI

A NEW DRONE DESIGN USING SIMPLE MECHANISMS BASED ON PD CONTROLLER

Dr. Zouaoui Satla

Department of Science and Technology, Faculty of Science and Technology.

University - Ahmed Ben Yehia ElWncharisi, Tissemsilt, Algeria.

Laboratory LMMS Sidi Bel Abbes.Algeria

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1142-4194>

Dr. Kouider Bendine

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Faculty of Science and Technology.

University – Dejlali Liabes, Sidi Bel Abbes, Algeria

Laboratory LMMS Sidi Bel Abbes.Algeria

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1842-5157>

Prof . Dr. Mohamed Elajrami

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Faculty of Science and Technology.

University – Dejlali Liabes, Sidi Bel Abbes, Algeria

Laboratory LMMS Sidi Bel Abbes.Algeria

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0928-6124>

Dr. Lakhdar Boumia

Department of Science and Technology, Faculty of Science and Technology.

University - Ahmed Ben Yehia ElWncharisi, Tissemsilt, Algeria.

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7693-7081>

ABSTRACT

The ornithopter-shaped ZK0.1 UAV, which is presented in this paper, is a revolutionary design for an unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV). The movement of the wings is managed by a straightforward system with three driving motors. The whole model was created in SOLIDWORKS, then control blocks were added using the SIMMECHANICS interface after export to MATLAB. To monitor the ZK0.1, a PD controller was attached to the blocks that had been previously detected. A tuning tool offered by MATLAB was used to define the PD settings. The simulations produced encouraging results, demonstrating that the suggested model may be used to a variety of situations due to its simplicity and ease of control. The work shows the potential for further research and

development in this field by providing a thorough method to developing and commanding a UAV with a new ornithopter design.

Keywords: Drone, ornithopter ZK0.1, solidworks, matlab/simulink, Simmechanics, PD controls.

1. INTRODUCTION

Drones have been widely incorporated into all facets of human existence in recent years. (Satla.Z.,2019) It may be found in every everyday routine and is used for a wide range of purposes, from sophisticated military operations to little playthings held by toddlers. As more applications emerge, particularly during the Covid-19 epidemic, which has created a new role such as sterilisation, protection, monitoring of epidemic hotspots, and supplying medical and food supply, this adaptability is growing even more. The design and development of drones has gained attention for the reasons previously indicated, and many researchers are concentrating on developing more dependable designs that are simple to monitor and build. (S. Zouaoui and All., 2018), (E. Mohamed et al., 2021), provided a straightforward methodology to decide the course and derive control parameters for drones using genetic algorithms. Additionally, the flight path of low-flying aircraft was examined (S. Róbert., 2020). (N.D. Dung., 2021) contains a study of several drone applications in smart cities.

Drones may be introduced as a replacement option in the near future for many industrial and private uses, particularly those relating to service delivery, rescue operations, and even farming. What opened up a space for study (S. Darvishpoor et al., 2020) that comprised biological drones known as ornithopters, development, and purification of numerous varieties that were touched upon and gathered the majority of them. A drone that flies by flapping its wings is known as an ornithopter (from the Greek *ornis*, ornith-"bird," and *pteron* "wing"). Designers have traditionally sought a substitute for the wing-flapping flying of insects, bats, and birds. Many scientists have seen a dearth of study on bio-mechanical aircraft, which they attribute to modelling difficulties compared to other types. However, there are studies that focus on these kinds, like (Y.W. Chin et al., 2020). Ornithopter devices are often built to the same standard as flying animals, despite their perhaps differing shapes. Larger helicopters were also created, some of which were largely successful and some of which were able to imitate bird flying in quality. Control, structure, and mechanism part design are only a few of the problems and obstacles that exist.

According to some study on the design and construction of UAV ornithopters, a novel model and development that flaps its wings at set amplitudes and varying frequencies has been proposed (Md. Nazmul Hasan et al., 2016). The use of a crank shaft system allowed the wings to move smoothly. A 100 watt DC motor with the required gearbox parts powered the model. A radio communication system and subsequently a tail that resembles a bird have been used for controlling and manoeuvring. Controlling the flapping frequency and tail combinations required three-channel radio communications. With this tail configuration, you can fly up, down, left, right, and 360 degrees. For the tail mechanism, micro servo motors were utilised. Consideration is given to the Design and Construction of an Autonomous Ornithopter (J. Grauer and J. Hubbard, 2010), The Phoenix is a large-scale ornithopter that the authors have created in order to more thoroughly examine the control of flapping wing flight. This kind has been constructed and examined of both the mechanical and electrical systems of the ornithopter as well as early control experiments. It is capable of carrying a substantial (400 gramme) computer and sensor package and is

specifically built for the application of controls research. The drone was put through extensive testing where it was required to stabilise the mechanism in pitch using a straightforward PD controller.

Following is how the remaining sections of the essay are structured: We describe the main physical, kinematic, and mechanical flying aspects of the ZK0.1 model in Section 2 of this paper. After implementing a Matlab/Simulink interface to connect Solidworks and Matlab, Section 3 explores the principles of the PD controller. The basic simulation findings of this work are presented in Section 4. The results of the paper are presented in a clear conclusion in Section 5.

2. MODEL DESCRIPTIONS

In order to make its pilots more effective and closely mimic the movements of a real bird, flapping wing ornithopter design still faces its greatest challenge: integrating relatively complex flapping and control mechanisms into a small, lightweight package that can be lifted by the thrust produced. The building of the model is accomplished in accordance with the diagram in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Diagram showing the design of the drone model and the research phases.

The proposed design consists of three main engines one located in the center of the model; this last is transferring a rotation movement to the mechanism actuator that shifts the wings. The mechanism is mainly used to transfer the rotation movement to a translation based with the help of Gear-shaft principle. The second and the third engines are located in the tail, their role is to rotate the tail up and down and right and left. As shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3.

Figure 2: The proposed design configuration of the ZK0.1.

Figure 3: The driven kinematics and flight dynamics of the ZK0.1.

3. PD CONTROLLER

The design is exported to Matlab/Simulink using the Simmechanics module in order to simulate the suggested model with the revised mechanism design shown in Figure 4. The transferring phase yields a block diagram presentation that includes all the components and the driving movement, as shown in Figures 5 and 6.

Figure 6: ZK0.1 Ornithopter model with subsystems blocks.

The control input u used to control the speed of motor and angles of servos and position of wings of the drone respect to the reference input designed as follows (S. Zouaoui, et all) and as the Figure 7 show :

$$u(t) = K_p e(t) + K_d \dot{e}(t). \quad (03)$$

K_p : is the proportional gain;

And K_d : is the derivation gain.

With error can be formulated as:

$$e(t) = s_p - p_v(t) \quad (04)$$

s_p : is the setpoint or desired position.

And $p_v(t)$: is the process variable at instantaneous time according to s_p . A high-quality controller must be able to establish a desired position. By using transfer function for motor, servo 01 and servo 02.

The controller block can be found in Figure 8 while the mathematical description is given in the previous paragraph.

Figure 07: PD controller

Figure 08: Simulink model of ZK0.1 ornithopter with PD controller.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 9, 10, and 11 illustrate, respectively, variations of responses of servo 01's between 20 and -20 degree and movement of second servo 02 responses over time between 1.5 and -1.5 degree and finally the response of the motor's rotation. The curves demonstrate that ZK0.1 is attempting the desired movement, demonstrating the precision of the current controller.

Figure 09: response of first servo with limitation angle between 20 and -20 degree.

Figure 10: response of first servo with limitation angle between 1.5 and -1.5 degree.

Figure 11: response of motor.

Figure 12 depicts how each wing moved during the simulation; during the first 10 seconds, there were some incomplete movements and the model had to be retained to respond in the first second. The stability of the movement of the two wings was then demonstrated by the findings.

Figure 12: movement of two wings amplitude.

5. CONCLUSION

In the cited study, modelling, stabilisation, and control of a tiny UAV ornithopter are discussed. Solidworks, a popular computer-aided design programme in engineering and architecture, is used by the writers to create the model ZK0.1 at the beginning. The model is connected with a proportional-integral-derivative (PID) control algorithm schema when the design is finished in order to mimic its dynamic behaviour following export to a MATLAB simscape model.

According to the simulation results, there is very little deviation for the two control angles between the necessary path and the simulation. Due to the second servomotor's neglected connection relationship with servomotor 1, the control of the second servomotor is less stable than the control of the first servomotor. This is due to the fact that the study is only a preliminary investigation of the novel and inventive design, and more study is required to properly optimize the model.

The proposed model has been shown to be stable and long-lasting despite this problem. In spite of being subjected to diverse disturbances, the study shows that the ornithopter can keep its indicated trajectory. In their conclusion, the authors recommend that future research concentrate on enhancing the design by giving the wings more features and regulating parameters with optimization algorithms.

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